

THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TALENT MANAGEMENT AND EMPLOYEE PRODUCTIVITY IN NIGERIAN FOOD AND BEVERAGE FIRMS

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Abstract

This study examined talent management and employee productivity in foods and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria: The mediating role of organizational commitment. The study specifically focus on the effect of talent management on employee productivity, effect of talent management on organizational commitment and the mediating role of organizational commitment in the relationship between talent management and employee productivity. The population of the study comprises of 6172 employees drawn from the selected foods and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria with the sample size of 399 using Taro Yamane's formula. Correlation and regression was used as a method of data analysis. The findings of the study revealed that, there is a significant and positive relationship between talent management, employee productivity and organizational commitment, and organizational commitment significantly mediate the relationship between talent management and employee productivity. The study recommend that management of foods and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria should adopt good policies of talent identification, attraction and retention of employees by providing financial and non –financial monetary rewards that will encourage employees to stay in a company and become committed to improve organizational productivity.

Keywords: Talent Management, Employee, Productivity, Organizational Commitment

1.0 Introduction

Increase worker output has been a top priority for many businesses. This is because increased productivity benefits both the company and its workers in terms of efficiency, effectiveness, creativity, and service quality (Damini, 2018). When productivity is high, the economy expands, businesses make a lot of money, and society improves. In addition, increased productivity can help businesses gain a competitive edge by decreasing expenses and boosting the quality of their products (Asep, 2022). Because of these gains, employee productivity is now an issue worth discussing. Engaged workers are thought to be more effective in their roles because they are driven to succeed by intrinsic rather than extrinsic motivations. They also have a sharper attention to detail than their unmotivated peers (Damini, 2018).

It is only fair to compare a worker's output to that of others who perform the same or similar tasks. Mehdi (2017) explains that workers' productivity can also be measured by the number of product or service units that a worker is responsible for handling in a certain period of time. Businesses, organizations, and institutions have made increasing employee productivity a priority since they have realized that it is crucial to their success (Jarvi, 2019). Employees' efficiency and effectiveness are the measures of employees' productivity, and if businesses in the

foods and beverage sector can find ways to attract employees who are competent, knowledgeable, skilled, and creative, they will see significant increases in productivity. Employees who have a sense of belonging to their company are more likely to go above and beyond in their work.

Organizational commitment has become the focus of managers and human resource departments in many organizations (Sopiah, 2020). The major responsibility of Human Resource (HR) managers is to understand the factors that generate employee commitment, and to use that knowledge to leverage employee retention and productivity. Organizational commitment describes the employee's position of commitment to the organization, as well as the employee's identification and dedication in enhancing the achievement of organizational goal (Oganezi, 2017). The globalization of the labor force through advances in computer technology and telecommunication has created more challenges for managers as their task in attracting talents and ensuring an environment where those employees can contribute as long-term assets to the organization is becoming increasingly difficult, when organizations can employ, train, and maintain skilled individuals, the overall stability of such organizations is enhanced, both in terms of productivity and financial viability (Wasnar, 2020). Therefore, organizational commitment is a crucial and desirable element in employee's behavior in workplaces and organizations.

The importance of organizational commitment may be credited to the fact that organizational commitment leads to several favorable outcomes for both individuals and organization (Arian, 2020). However, Organizational commitment has also gained interest as it is seen as the core component for cooperation and consensus in a functionally cohesive organization. It is suggested that employees are more empowered to serve the common goal in strong, cohesive organizations, while the attractiveness of values brings members of the organization closer together. As such, having reliable employees is very significant for organizations since there is evidence that loyal or reliable employees add to the value of an organization, which help in attracting and retaining best individuals (Beluchi, 2020). The theoretical overview of organizational commitment, showed the difference between attitudinal commitment and behavioral commitment. If employees are highly committed to their organization, they will specify their objectives and values, and at the same time, have a great desire to become their member and be ready to express positive organizational citizenship behaviors. Such employees will be willing to do more work outside their duties and responsibilities and always make the best efforts in the organization. Contrary, if employees are not commitment, they will be non-contributive, and also inclined to leave the organization (Englert, 2018).

Companies are under increasing pressure to outperform their past achievements in today's competitive global business climate. The ability of an organization to generate and store information has grown in importance as a means of increasing its competitiveness and adaptability to market shifts throughout time (Patricia, 2020). The Human Resources division is responsible for the time-consuming process of identifying and cultivating employees with exceptional abilities or leadership potential (Oluyemi, 2020), which is just as important as any other critical strategic function. Investment in talented human capital is the most significant challenge affecting the growth and development of businesses, companies, or organizations locally and internationally (Basiron, 2020). Human resources are crucial for the long-term viability of business organizations. Having talented and capable people

who can be considered a competitive advantage of the organization and who can also contribute skillfully to the success of the organization is a global concern of business organizations (Ndolo, 2017).

Because of the increasingly competitive business environment, human resources are increasingly seen as a company's most valuable asset (Fatemeh, 2019). Organizations in today's highly competitive corporate environment are actively seeking out ways to attract top talented workers, and those who fail to do so will find it extremely difficult, if not impossible, to achieve their strategic objectives (Dayel, 2020). Competition among businesses is driven by employees' abilities; the companies that can attract and keep the most talented workers have the best chance of increasing their market share and bottom line (Rezaian & Soltani, 2019).

To put it simply, talent management is the process of identifying and nurturing and retaining organization's most valuable, skillful and talented employees. According to Fatemeh (2019), talent management is "a process for maximizing an organization's effectiveness in attracting, developing, deploying, and retaining its most valuable human resource."

1.2. Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of talent management on employee productivity in Foods and Beverage manufacturing organizations in Nigeria: The mediating role of organizational commitment. The specific objectives of the study includes to:

- i. Evaluate the effect of talent management on organizational commitment of listed Foods and Beverage Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria.
- ii. Examine the effect of talent management on employee productivity of Foods and Beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria
- iii. Determine the mediating role of organizational commitment in the relationship between talent management and employee productivity of listed Foods and Beverage Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Clarification

2.1.2 Concept of Talent Management

Different academics have come up with different definitions of "talent management" to express how they think of it. Today, businesses have varying perspectives on what constitutes effective talent management. The reason for this is that there are disagreements and misunderstandings in the technical aspects of talent management inside many organisations. That is to say, in some companies, HR tasks and talent management practices are intertwined and difficult to disentangle. In addition, talent management is implemented differently by different companies. Nonetheless, talent management is a part of HRM activities that are evaluated in two ways: first, in terms of the HRM department's ability to coordinate and interact with the various parts of the HR function; and second, in terms of its effectiveness as a strategic partner in helping the organization achieve its goals. A study by Mujdelen, Gulruh, and Pinar (2017). Talent management, on the other hand, involves identifying, recruiting, and retaining top personnel to advance an organization's objectives. This evolved from traditional methods of managing employees into the more modern strategic approach to human resources. The many and varied definitions of talent

management concepts are an obvious result of the many and varied approaches to talent management. In reality, talent is context dependent and shifts with time.

Beluchi (2020), define talent management as "a set of strategies and systems to increase productivity by developing improved processes for attracting, developing, retaining, and utilising people with the required skills and aptitude to meet current and future business needs." According to the researcher's perspective, talent management is seen as the methodical process of hiring, developing, and retaining individuals to maximize an organization's potential. Effective talent management ensures that a company has access to enough qualified workers to meet its current and future demands. Macha (2020) argues that the success of companies depends on their people management strategies because the top companies have the best employees. According to the study's authors, it's also a method used to find qualified workers for a company. Organizational strength can be increased by talent management (Odegov, 2021). Mehdi (2017) defines talent management as "the process of identifying, attracting, developing, and deploying people who are likely to be strategically important to an organization both now and in the future." By focusing on identifying, developing, appraising, deploying, and retaining high-performing and high-potential personnel, talent management may be utilised as a tool to manage the best-in-class talent (Anoop, 2019). In managing employee talent an organization should ensure that, the appropriate people or individuals are assign in the right roles. Although talent management is intended to aid in the accomplishment of an organization's long-term strategic goals, many businesses view it as a temporary initiative.

Talent management, according to Tyskbo (2019), is the study of optimizing organizational performance through the use of human resource strategy. The foregoing interpretation demonstrates that talent management entails selecting employees from the talent pool, retaining them, and providing continuing training and development programmers to improve their skills, by increasing organizational productivity. In order to be effective, a talent management plan must be tied to both the overall corporate strategy and the specifics of a given location. Beluchi (2020) define talent management as "the systematic, organized, and strategic process of attracting and retaining high-quality talent with the goal of maximizing each individual's contribution to achieving the organization's goals."

2.1.3. Organizational Commitment

Organizations depend on human resources they possess. Human resources are considered as the main element that make an organization perform without them nothing in an organization would get done (Shuyang, 2020). Attracting and retaining the best is the goal of every organization, but this is easier said than done. One of the major problems organizations face is the loss of their human resources. When employees leave the organization, it does not only mean a reduction in the number of employees, but also the loss of knowledge and experiences they have accumulated over the years (Nwoke,2021; Ndolo, 2017; Obeidat et al., 2014; Masa'deh et al., 2015; Obeidat et al., 2017).

Furthermore, the loss of human resources may not only be physical, it may also mean that the employee is present physically, but is absent-minded most of the time thinking of their own problems. This may also cause problems for organizations as employees are not giving their overall best to their work and the organization. Therefore, organizational commitment is regarded as a crucial and desirable element in employees' behavior, and it is seen

as elusive in workplaces and organizations (Najim, 2016). The importance given to organizational commitment may be attributed to the fact that organizational commitment leads to several favorable outcomes for both individuals and organizations (Chiu & Ng, 2015).

Organizational commitment has also gained interest as it is seen as the core component for cooperation and consensus in a functionally cohesive organization. It is suggested that employees are more empowered to serve the common goal in strong, cohesive organizations, while the attractiveness of values brings the members of the organization closer together. As such, it can be concluded that having loyal employees is very important for organizations since there is evidence that loyal employees add to the value of an organization, which help in attracting and retaining the very best individuals (Dahshan, 2018). This importance has been recognized since the 1960s by some workplace scholars. Since then, organizational commitment has become one of the most frequently studied organizational construct. As a consequence of this long history, many conceptualizations emerged for organizational commitment (Sukarmin, 2022). According to Dajani (2015), commitment is an obliging force that directs behavior. It is anything more than a motive to engage in a particular course of action, or a positive attitude toward the entity that encourages the person to act in a way that benefits that entity. Accordingly, organizational commitment is defined as the tendency, based on cognitive, affective, and normative forces on the individual, to behave in ways which place primacy on the promotion and protection of the interests of the organization as opposed to a preoccupation with the immediate/direct personal or sub-group interests (Beatus, 2017). From the foregoing, organizational commitment is the loyalty of employees in an organization or the level of attachment demonstrated by an employee in a company or organization.

2.1.4 Dimensions of Organizational Commitment

Meyer and Allen (1991, 1997) developed a model for organizational commitment that consists of three dimensions: affective, continuance, and normative commitment. These dimensions have been adopted in this study to justify reasons that make employees to be committed in an organization.

i. Affective Commitment

Affective or moral commitment occurs when individuals fully embrace the goals and values of the organization. They become emotionally involved with the organization and feel personally responsible for the organization's level of success. These individuals usually demonstrate high levels of performance, positive work attitudes, and a desire to remain with the organization (Basel, 2019). Affective commitment is the most powerful of organizational commitment as it is based on intrinsic, rather than, extrinsic motivation (Hayoung, 2021). This type of commitment forms over time as a result of positive treatment by the organization (Lambert et al., 2015). Affective commitment develops when an individual becomes involved in recognizing the value-relevance of, or derives his/her identity from the organization. Employees are considered affectively committed if they feel that the organization treats them in a fair, respectful, and supporting manner (Esfahani et al., 2014). Affective commitment refers to an individual's positive feeling towards and willingness to be emotionally attached to the organization (Bell-Ellis et al., 2015). It includes the core elements of loyalty to the organization, identification with the organization, and

involvement in the organization. The essence of this kind of commitment comes from the idea that individuals choose to, and want to remain in the organization (Lambert et al., 2015).

Several factors have been reported to influence the development of affective commitment. These factors range from organizational characteristics and personal characteristics to work experiences. Organizational characteristics include organizational culture and some organizational-level policies. Most importantly, perceptions of justice and fairness of organizational policies have been reported to play a significant role in the development of affective commitment (Singh, 2015). Personal characteristics include demographic variables such as age, gender, and job tenure, in addition to dispositional variables such as personality traits and values. Work experiences have been found to be correlated with affective commitment. Such variables include job challenge, degree of autonomy, and variety of skills used by employees Dessler, (2015). It has been further suggested that factors like type of business, positions, and number of employees might have an influence on the affective commitment of employees (Mir, 2021). The huge interest in studying affective commitment can be attributed to the fact that it has an effect on many individual attitudes and behaviors in the workplace (Yousaf, 2015). Among all the forms of commitment, affective commitment has been recognized as having the strongest correlation with positive organizational outcomes and individual outcomes (Bell-Ellis, 2015) outweighing the effects of the continuance and normative components of commitment (Sinan, 2021). Therefore, it is suggested that affective commitment leads to reduced stress, reduced work-family conflict, lower turnover, reduced absenteeism, improved performance, and increased organizational productivity and commitment. Based on the foregoing view of scholars, Affective commitment is simply the emotional attachment of an employee in a company.

ii. **Continuance Commitment**

Continuance or calculative commitment occurs when individuals base their relationship with the organization on what they are receiving in return for their efforts and what would be lost if they were to leave (i.e., pay, benefits, associations). These individuals put forth their best effort only when the rewards match their expectations (Fard, 2015). Continuance commitment refers to the awareness of the cost associated with leaving the organization (Arun, 2018). It is related to the performance required to keep a job and the costs encountered by leaving the organization (Bell-Ellis, 2015). Continuance commitment develops an employee discover that they stand to lose investment in the organization, or realize that no alternatives exist other than remaining in the organization (Dhanalakshmi, 2014). These investments include physical, cognitive, and emotional investments such as salary and benefits, retirement plans, skills, social relationship, and lost opportunities (Lambert et al., 2015). Another classification of investments made in the organization includes financial investments such as pay, benefits, job security, and retirement money; and non-financial investments such as status and friendship with colleagues (Aysen, 2018). As such, the employees bond with the organization because they must do so and are compelled to do so (Lambert et al., 2015). To the researcher this type of organizational commitment occur due to loss of economic benefits and the inability of the employee to get a new job due to unemployment.

Some of the factors that may lead to the development of continuance commitment include age, tenure, career satisfaction, and intent (Kont & Jantson, 2014). Employees with strong continuance commitment will not be motivated to contribute to the organization beyond what is needed to keep their jobs. Consequently, this type of

commitment may be negatively related to work behaviors (Englert, 2018). This is supported by Allen and Englert, (2018) who stated that “in the absence of other reasons for staying, those with strong continuance commitment might feel particularly resentful of the situation in which they find themselves; potentially, this could lead to undesirable work behavior in the foods and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria. From the reviewed literature on continuance commitment, it simply means employees are committed in an organisation base on economic gains.

iii. **Normative Commitment**

Normative commitment occurs when individuals remain with an organization based on expected standards of behavior or social norms. These individuals value obedience, cautiousness, and formality. Research suggests that they tend to display the same attitudes and behaviors as those who have affective commitment. Normative commitment is a form of obligation toward the organization due to a person’s moral belief that it is the right and moral thing to stay in the organization. As such, people with a high normative commitment remain in the organization because they believe they ought to (Aysen, 2018). Normative commitment develops when individuals internalize the norms of the organization through socialization, receive benefits that induce them to feel the need to reciprocate, or accept the terms of a psychological contract. This can be the result of the process of internalization individuals undergo before or after joining the organization (Englert, 2018). The researcher views normative commitment as the situation in which an individual remains in an organization base on moral reasons. Some of the most important factors that have an influence on the way normative commitment is experienced are leadership and culture (Jung, 2016) Leadership plays a significant role in inducing normative commitment by demonstrating high levels of moral standards, honesty, and integrity. With regards to culture, different cultural factors influence the interpretation and implications of normative commitment in different ways (Ingram, 2016) Järvi (2016), indicates that normative commitment is expected to be greater and related more strongly to behaviors in collectivist cultures as opposed to individualistic cultures. Other cultural factors that are argued to affect normative commitment are power distance and future orientation amongst others (Christy, 2017). Employees with normative commitment are predicted to make positive contributions to the organization. However, compared to affective commitment, these contributions tend to be smaller as employees do not carry with them the same feelings of enthusiasm and involvement. Furthermore, employees with normative commitment might feel resentful of their feelings of indebtedness to brewery, foods/ beverage manufacturing companies thereby affecting the way they perform their work duties (Kamel, 2019). From the above reviewed views on normative commitment, it is the level of commitment exhibited by an employee in a company base on his or her moral values.

Looking at the above three dimensions of organizational commitment, the researcher adopted affective commitment in this study, this is because the willingness of an individual to accept the goals and values of a company or organisation and his ability to contribute his creative and innovative ideas for the achievement of the company objectives will enhanced more productivity than other components of organizational commitment.

2.1.5. Employee Productivity

Iuhia (2012) defines productivity as "the amount and quality of work done, adjusted for the cost of the resources used." Ibhagui (2017) defines employee productivity as "the amount of goods and services produced by an

employee in a given period of time using available resources, machines, and environment in order to improve the standard of living, economic growth, production margin, profit maximization, and organizational competitiveness." Workers are considered productive if they are successful in accomplishing their objectives through the efficient use of available resources.

The competitive edge of a company increases in proportion to its employees' productivity. This is because everything has been utilized so effectively. According to Ibhagui (2017), "results" are the ultimate and measurable outcomes of an employee's efforts. Whether monetary or social in nature, their outcomes are often measured in terms of cost, quality, quantity, and time. The time it takes the typical worker to do a certain amount of work is one way of gauging productivity, according to Ramanujam (2014). Time spent on operations like production, travel, or waiting for materials or repairing damaged equipment by a team of workers is another example. This technique can help businesses see if their workers are spending too much time on non-production related tasks.

Profitability is directly related to employee productivity, which can be difficult to quantify. Employers are more likely to be content with their workforce if they are able to find and hire competent and talented workers who will contribute to the company's success from the outset of their employment. A number of things, however, can increase an employee's productivity on the work (Saxena, 2015). According to Sharma (2014), human resources receive the most scrutiny of any resource utilized to boost efficiency in businesses. A large portion of an HR system's efforts are focused on improving worker or company output. Human resources tasks including pay, appraisal systems, training, selection, job design, and compensation all have a direct bearing on output. The researcher found that boosting employee productivity was a top concern for many modern businesses, including breweries and food and beverage producers. Productivity measures the effectiveness of an individual worker or a team. Productivity, in reality, is a factor that has an immediate impact on the bottom line.

An employee's production during a certain time frame can be used as a proxy for their productivity. A worker's productivity is typically measured in comparison to the typical production of their peers. It can also be measured by the number of products or services an employee is responsible for per given time period. The efficiency of its workforce is also crucial to its overall performance. As a result, maximizing worker output has emerged as a top priority for many companies. In addition, (Ibhagui, 2019) argues that a competitive advantage can be attained through Human Resource Management (HRM) by reducing labour costs and raising productivity via the creation of more direct ties between compensation and performance. There has been a resurgence of interest in techniques meant to inspire workers to priorities satisfying customers and increasing output in response to rising productivity and customer service issues.

2.2. Effect of Talent management on organizational Commitment

Talent management has largely focused on the economic aspect of work, with the aim of maximizing shareholders wealth (Collings, 2014). This has led to an incomplete understanding of talent management practices as a result of having failed to consider their non- economic value or the interests of the organization's employees (Gallardo & Thunnissen, 2016; Thunnissen, 2016). Therefore, the more companies take into account employees' objectives, the more motivated employees will be and the more they will contribute to the organization (Collings, 2014). In fact, employees will perform better if they perceive equity in the treatment received, and if they feel their talent

and skills are being recognized at work (Bjorkman et al., 2013). Thus, if they receive different economic and non-economic compensations (Boxall, 2013, Kates, 2006) they will be more linked to the organization. It should also be remembered that the notion of talent may differ between employee and company management. Should these notions not be aligned, the company's anticipated impact on the desired organizational behaviour of employees may be lost (Sonnenber, 2014)

In a similar vein, the current trend is towards changing jobs as other job offers adjust better to employees' talent and preferences (Bidwell and Briscoe, 2010, Michaels et al., 2001, Oladapo, 2014). People who have more talent are more employable and are therefore those most likely to leave the organization and get better jobs. This has been called dysfunctional turnover. For this reason, work commitment, as a retention strategy, becomes a key variable in talent management. Organizational commitment reflects the degree to which people in the organization identify and participate with it (Mowday et al., 1982), and focuses on employee retention and turnover (Meyer et al., 2004). The more committed the employees are, the more they wish to contribute to improving the organization (Mowday et al., 1982, Collings and Mellahi, 2009, Tansley, 2011). In addition, HR professionals suggest that the retention of high Performers is a crucial issue for the organization (Sturman et al., 2003). Kumar and Raghavendran (2013) state that employees are committed to their company when they know the value of their work and the impact it has on customers. For this reason, the company must display an interest in knowing what employees like to do, what they do best and what brings most value to the company. Companies that have valuable people but who are under committed will find themselves with talented employees but not with committed employees. For their part, companies with low-value and high-commitment personnel will obtain mediocre results (Luna-Arocas and Morley, 2015). Employees identified as high potential have less tendency to leave the organization if the commitment in the relationship mediates (Malik et al., 2017). In this way, if employees perceive that they are identified as a talent in the organization, greater commitment is obtained compared to those who do not perceive that they are identified as such or with those who do not know it (Björkman, 2013).

TM practices and activities are aimed at attracting, selecting, hiring, developing, and retaining talent (Thunnissen et al., 2013, Oladapo, 2014). Organizations must focus not only on the first three, but on developing and retaining talent, as these will be the ones that provide superior results (Oladapo, 2014). Moreover, technological progress has generated a demand for talented professionals who, among other things, place a high value on the autonomy and meaning of their connection with work (Kumar & Raghavendran, 2013). In order to better understand these TM practices, it is necessary to analyze the perception and evaluation carried out by employees.

2.3 Mediating Role of Organizational Commitment in the Relationship between Talent Management and Employee Productivity

Talent management is an important tool that needs to be implemented by an organization or a company. Talent management is essentially a series of processes carried out by the company to identify, develop, maintain, and place the right people at the right place. Talent management policies can influence employee productivity and also improve employee commitment to an organization. (Dhanalakshmi & Gurunathan 2014); (Mensah et al. 2016) proposed that talent management has a relationship with employee productivity, and it is mediated by organizational commitment as well as how they identify with the company. Besides, Mohammed (2016) remarked

that talent management has a relationship with employee productivity through organizational commitment. Kamel (2019) noted that talent management is a business strategy in an organization, which potentially promotes organization accomplishment. In other words, when worker or employee has particular competence that is difficult to be adopted by others, the organization will have a competitive advantage over competitors. This prove that, talent management influences company productivity through employee involvement. Therefore, this relationship is shown in the diagram below;

Source: Field Survey 2023

2.4 Theoretical Framework

2.4. 1. Human Capital Theory (1961)

This study adopted Human Capital Theory propounded by Schultz (1961); and developed by Becker (1994). The human capital theory suggests that education or training raises the productivity of workers by imparting useful knowledge and skills, hence raising workers’ future income by increasing their lifetime earnings (Becker, 1994). The human capital theory states that an individual’s decision to invest in training is based upon an examination of the net present value of the costs and benefits of such an investment. Individuals are assumed to invest in training during an initial period and receive returns to the investment in subsequent periods. In this view, human capital is similar to “physical means of production”, e.g. factories and machines: one can invest in human capital (via education, training, medical treatment) and one’s outputs depend partly on the rate of return on the human capital on owns.

The human capital theory prescribes education, training and skills acquisitions as mechanisms for attaining productivity, workers efficiency and overall social-economic development. The spending on human capital (workforce) is a worthwhile and productive investment similar to investment in nation’s physical assets (Kim,

2017). The human capital theory advocates education and training as a tool for improving human capital, stimulating labour productivity and boosting the levels of technology across the globe. Human capital enhancement through quality education and training is a critical factor that is responsible for economic growth and development of nations. While formal education has expanded rapidly in many countries, a large portion of human capital accumulation in the forms of on-the-job training and other modes for working adults actually take place both inside and outside the workplace Anwar, (2014).

The biggest challenge to human capital theory as pointed out by Calvin (2016) is underemployment of credentialed knowledge that is, a large number of people who have invested many years of their lives in acquiring advanced formal educational qualifications, are unable to obtain commensurate jobs. Such situation is prevalent in most of the underdeveloped countries like Nigeria. Another shortcoming of human capital theory is that in countries like Nigeria, more emphasis is given to paper qualification rather than employee’s skills and talents.

The human capital theory is relevant to this study because the theory proposes that people’s skills, experience, and knowledge are a form of capital and that returns are earned from investments made by the employer or employee to develop these attributes. The theory holds that employers should invest in specific training and further initiation of more promotion opportunities to enhance employee’s career path prospects. The theory is also relevant to this study because in order to enhance the job performance of breweries, foods/ beverage manufacturing companies then, more effort should be made to facilitate training programmers if they perceive that this would be valuable. The theory is relevant to this study because, if breweries, foods/ beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria invest in the training and developing of employees to acquire skills and knowledge, it will help to boost the productivity of the company. Also, the quality of the output will improve, resulting ton increase in sales and profitability of the company.

3.1 Methodology

This study adopted survey design since it involves the field enquiries by collecting data using questionnaire from the target population. The target population of this study consists of 6172 staff drawn from Nigerian Breweries, Dangote sugar Refinery, International Breweries, Northern Nigeria flour mills and Cadbury Nigeria Plc. The study adopted a sample size of

399 using Taro Yamane’s formula. The data collected from participants were analyzed using correlation coefficient and regression analysis. Formulated hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 23) software.

3.2 Results and Discussion

The data collected from respondents were analyzed and presented using correlation and regression in the Tables below: **Table 1: Correlations Matrix**

	Talent (TM)	Management Organizational Commitment (OC)
Pearson Correlation	1	.785**
TM Sig. (2-tailed)		.000

	N	380	380
	Pearson Correlation	.785**	1
OC	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	380	380

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2022.

The result in Table 1 shows the correlation between talent management and organizational commitment. The result showed that talent management had high correlation with organizational commitment ($r=.785$; $p<.01$).

Table 2: Correlations Matrix

		Talent (TM)	Management Employee Productivity (EP)
TM	Pearson Correlation	1	.693**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	380	380
EP	Pearson Correlation	.693**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	380	380

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2022.

The result in Table 2 indicates the correlation between talent management on organizational employee productivity. The result reported a positive and significant relationship between talent management and employee productivity ($r=.693$; $p<.01$).

Table 3: Regression Model and Test of Hypotheses

Variables	β	T	Sig.	Remark
Talent Management → OC	.294	2.333	.013	Supported
Talent Management → EP	.278	2.292	.024	Supported

Commitment

R-Squared .785

Adjusted R-Squared .769

F. statistic	218.463
Prob (F-statistics)	.000
Durbin-watson statistic	1.682

Organizational EP .292 2.638 .006 Supported

Predictors: (Constant), Talent Management

Dependent Variable: Employee productivity

Mediating Variable: Organizational Commitment

Source: Researcher’s Computation from SPSS Output, 2022.

The results of the regression model as in Table 3 showed that the explanatory variables accounted for 78% variability in the dependent variable (employee productivity) as explained by the coefficient of determination ($R^2=0.785$). The overall test (F-statistic) (goodness-of-fit measure) shows a value of 218.463 and this implies that the overall result was statistically significant. The Durbin-Watson value of 1.682 indicated that there was no collinearity issue with the model.

The results of multiple regressions, as presented in Table 3 revealed that all the hypotheses earlier formulate were rejected. The result of hypothesis one (H_{01}) showed that talent management has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment of listed

Foods and Beverage Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria ($\beta= 0.294$; $t=2.333$; $p=0.013$

<0.05). The null hypothesis which states that talent management has no significant on organizational commitment of listed Brewery, Foods and Beverage Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria was rejected.

The test of hypothesis two (H_{02}) indicated that talent management has a positive and significant effect on employee productivity in listed Foods and Beverage Manufacturing

Companies in Nigeria ($\beta= 0.278$; $t=2.292$; $p=0.024 < 0.05$). Therefore, the study rejects the null hypothesis (H_{02}).

Hypothesis three (H_{03}) stated that organizational commitment does not mediate the relationship between talent management and employee productivity and the result indicated that organizational commitment significantly mediate the relationship between talent management and employee productivity in listed Foods and Beverage Manufacturing

Companies in Nigeria ($\beta= 0.292$; $t=2.638$; $p=0.006 < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{03}) was rejected.

4.1 Discussion of Findings

The result of tested hypothesis indicated that talent management has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment of listed Foods and Beverage Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria. This finding is supported by Björkman (2013) who reported that if employees perceive that they are identified as a talent in the organization greater commitment is obtained compared to those who do not perceive that they are identified as such. In agreement with the finding Oladapo (2014) averred that the development and retaining of talent by organizations will help employees to provide superior results. In their study, Dhanalakshmi and Gurunathan (2014) stated that talent management policies influence employee productivity and their commitment to an organization.

Findings of the study also indicated that organizational commitment played in significant role in mediating the relationship between talent management and employee productivity of listed Foods and Beverage Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria. The result is in line with Kumar and Raghavendran (2013) who affirmed that employees are committed to their company when they know the value of their work and the impact it has on customers. Malik et al. (2017) in their study stated that employees identified as high potential have fewer tendencies to leave the organization if the commitment in the relationship mediates. Also, Mohammed (2016) established that talent management has a relationship with employee productivity through organizational commitment.

5.0 Conclusion

The study investigated talent management and employee productivity in foods and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria: The mediating role of organizational commitment. The findings of the study result to the conclusion that, talent management has a positive and significant effect on employee productivity and organizational commitment of listed Foods and Beverage Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria and organizational commitment significantly mediate the relationship between talent management and employee productivity in listed Foods and Beverage Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the research and conclusion drawn, this study recommends as follows;

- i. Management of foods and beverage companies should continue to review their policy document that heavily rely on talent identification, attraction, development and retention that are dependent on the commitment they place or pledge their employees. The partial effect of employee commitment is borne out of the quest for management to control their investment and commitment to employee welfare and when priorities are not set straight, company managers may be at the receiving end when employees begin to agitate for improved working conditions and general welfare.
- ii. Management of food and beverages companies should continue to pursue talent hunt and development in areas such as offering on the job and off- the job training to nurture and improve employee skills, provision of training programmes by organizations that improves effective performance of employees and mentoring, coaching and rotating employees in a company for improved employees' skills and productivity.
- iii. Management of foods and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria should consider organizational commitment as a mandatory prerequisite for improved employee productivity. This is because employees may be more committed in an organization based on the economic gains they derive from working in the organization. As such they find it difficult to leave thereby promoting work-life balance and socially supportive policies, boost employees feeling of loyalty to the company that lead to improved employee productivity.

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